

Geometric Analysis of a Deltoid Area Formed by The Intersection of Two Circles

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the region formed by the intersection of two circles from a geometric perspective. The intersection scenarios were evaluated based on whether the radii of the circles were equal or different. When the circles intersect, a line segment is formed by connecting the two points obtained, and this segment, together with the line passing through the centres of the circles, forms the basis of a rectangle with perpendicular diagonals. The study examined the relationship between the radii of the circles and the diagonal lengths of the rectangle, and in this context, a formula was obtained that gives the area of the rectangle formed in the intersection region. The analyses showed that the area of the quadrilateral can be calculated if the radii of the circles and the length of the line segment passing through the centres in the intersection region are known. Furthermore, it was determined that the area of the quadrilateral increases up to a certain point depending on the positions of the circles and then begins to decrease, and the maximum and minimum area values were determined accordingly.

Keywords: *Circle, Intersection Region, Quadrilateral, Deltoid, Area Calculation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics has been one of the most important disciplines guiding humanity's quest for order, symmetry, and aesthetics throughout history. Geometry, in particular, highlights the aesthetic aspect of mathematics by enabling the visualisation of shapes, the revelation of relationships between them, and the formulation of generalisations from these relationships (Köse, 2008). The integration of geometric structures with aesthetics and symmetry has had a profound impact not only in mathematics but also in disciplines such as architecture and art (Pesen, 2002). In this context, the circle has played a central role both in daily life and in mathematical thinking, becoming one of the most fundamental and striking shapes in geometry.

A circle is defined as the set of points in a plane that are equidistant from a fixed point. This fixed point is called the centre of the circle, and the equal distance is called the radius (MEB, 2019). Euclid emphasised the fundamental property of the circle in his third postulate, stating, 'It is possible to define a circle with a centre and a radius' (Aslan, 2013). Since ancient times, the circle has been an important subject of research in both theoretical and applied mathematics.

The intersection of two circles presents a special case for mathematical analysis. When circles intersect at two points, the line segment connecting these points allows a quadrilateral with perpendicular diagonals to form in the intersection region. Due to its perpendicular diagonals, this quadrilateral is called a deltoid (Küpeli, 2019). The symmetrical structure of the deltoid offers a powerful advantage in area calculations. In particular, the Pythagorean Theorem serves as a fundamental tool for determining the area based on the lengths of the deltoid's diagonals. This classical theorem, with its proposition that 'In a right triangle, the sum of the squares of the two legs is equal to the square of the hypotenuse' (Proclus, 1970), provides a directly applicable method in the context of the deltoid.

The study of geometric structures arising from circle intersections not only demonstrates the applicability of classical theorems to contemporary problems but also contributes to the discovery of mathematical aesthetics. Indeed, the study *Mathematical Circles (Russian Experience)* (Genkin, Fomin & Itenberg, 1996) emphasises that using circle intersections as a pedagogical tool develops problem-solving and mathematical discovery skills in students.

This study aims to mathematically examine the area of the deltoid obtained from the intersection of two circles. Symmetry, geometric reasoning and the Pythagorean Theorem are considered together to develop both an algebraic

and a geometric approach. Thus, the aim is not only to arrive at a specific area formula, but also to reinterpret mathematical aesthetics through a contemporary problem.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, two circles with given radius lengths were moved towards each other along a straight line passing through their centres to create intersection regions. The intersection conditions were examined separately according to whether the radii of the circles were equal or different.

When the radii are equal

If the radii of these circles are equal, the following situations occur:

- When the circles intersect at only one point, this intersection is tangential and no intersection region is formed.

Figure 1. Intersection of two circles with equal radii at one point.

- When the circles intersect at two points, connecting these points yields a line segment, which is used as one of the diagonals of the quadrilateral.

Figure 2. Intersection of two circles with equal radii at two points (two examples).

- If the circles coincide completely, the intersection area reaches its maximum size.

Figure 3. The situation where two circles with equal radii coincide.

The case where the radii are different

If the radius lengths of these circles are different, the following situations occur:

- When the circles intersect at one point, they are again only tangent and no intersection region is formed.

Figure 4. Intersection of two circles with different radii at one point.

- When they intersect at two points, the line segment connecting these points again forms one of the diagonals of the quadrilateral.

Figure 5. Intersection of two circles with different radii at two points (two examples).

- When their centres coincide, the intersection region is bounded by the area of the circle with the smaller radius.

Figure 6. Coincidence of the centres of two circles with different radii

Any two circles with centres (points A and B) on line d, when moved towards each other along line d from their centres, intersect first at point C, as seen in Figure 7, and then, when the movement continues, at points C and D, as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Point C where any two circles with centres A and B intersect.

Figure 8. Points C and D where any two circles with centres A and B intersect.

Since circles intersecting at a single point do not form any intersection region, the expression zero can be used for the area of the quadrilateral expected to form in the intersection region. Furthermore, two different situations arise where the area of the quadrilateral formed by moving any two circles along line d is maximised. When the radii of the circles are equal, the intersection area of the circles is the entire circle, so a line f perpendicular to line d is drawn, and the points where these two lines intersect the circle's circumference are connected to form the quadrilateral area, as shown in Figure 9. When the radii of the circles are different, since the area of the smaller radius circle is the intersection area of the circles, a line f perpendicular to line d is drawn, and the points where these two lines intersect on the circumference of the smaller radius circle are connected to form the area of the quadrilateral inside the smaller radius circle, as shown in Figure 10. Since the radii of the circles can be equal or different, the cases of inequality and equality in relation to the radii of the circles were examined.

Figure 9. The quadrilateral with the largest area in the intersection region formed by the areas of two circles with equal radii.

Figure 10. The quadrilateral with the largest area in the intersection region formed by the areas of two circles with different radii.

There is the following relationship between the intersection of the circles and the area of the quadrilateral.

- a. If the circles intersect at one point, the area of the quadrilateral is zero because no quadrilateral is formed.
- b. If the circles intersect at two points, the area changes as the circles move towards each other, and finally, when the centres of the circles coincide, the area of the quadrilateral reaches its maximum.

In both cases, a quadrilateral has been formed by considering the line segment connecting the intersection points of the circles and the intersection region on the line passing through the centres. The area of this quadrilateral has been calculated based on the lengths of its diagonals. GeoGebra software was used to test the accuracy of the area calculations. The Pythagorean Theorem was primarily used in the area calculations. The relationship between the radii of the circles and the diagonal passing through the intersection point was modelled using right-angled triangles, and the area formula for the quadrilateral was derived through this relationship.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 11 shows that the CEDF quadrilateral is formed by the intersection of points C and D, where the centres of any two circles (points A and B) move along line d, and the intersection of points E and F, where line d intersects the intersection region.

Figure 11. CEDF Quadrilateral Region

To find the area of the quadrilateral based on the lengths of its diagonals, points C and D are connected, as shown in Figure 12. The resulting diagonals are perpendicular to each other. Using the lengths of the resulting $|CD|$ diagonal and $|EF|$ diagonal, the area of the quadrilateral is found as $\frac{|CD| \cdot |EF|}{2}$. It is also clear that the area of the quadrilateral changes when centres A and B are moved along line d. Consequently, the diagonal lengths of the quadrilateral will also change.

Figure 12. Diagonals $|CD|$ and $|EF|$ of the quadrilateral

In Figure 13, since the CEDF quadrilateral divides the d line into two equal triangular regions, calculations are performed on the CEF triangle because finding the area of one of the triangular regions will help calculate the area of the quadrilateral.

Figure 13. CEF triangle belonging to the CEDF quadrilateral

Moving the centres of the circles centred at A and B along line d will change the length of $|EF|$ and the length of $|CG|$ on triangle CEF. With this change, the area of triangle CEF can be found using the formula $\frac{|CG| \cdot |EF|}{2}$. We can express the relationship between the length $|CG|$, which is the height of the CEF triangle, the radius of the circles centred at A and B, and the length $|EF|$ using the Pythagorean theorem. The lengths given for this expression are symbolised by letters in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Lengths symbolised by letters

$$|AC| = r_a, \quad |CF| = r_b, \quad |CG| = h, \quad |EG| = b, \quad |GF| = c, |EF| = a;$$

The length h is found using Pythagoras' theorem as follows;

$$\text{With the radius of circle A, } h^2 = r_a^2 - (r_a - c)^2$$

$$\text{With the radius of circle B, } h^2 = r_b^2 - (r_b - b)^2$$

In this case, $h^2 = r_a^2 - (r_a - c)^2 = r_b^2 - (r_b - b)^2$ will be true.

Therefore;

$$r_a^2 - (r_a - c)^2 = r_b^2 - (r_b - b)^2$$

$$r_a^2 - (r_a^2 - 2r_a c + c^2) = r_b^2 - (r_b^2 - 2r_b b + b^2)$$

$$r_a^2 - r_a^2 + 2r_a c - c^2 = r_b^2 - r_b^2 + 2r_b b - b^2$$

$$2r_a c - c^2 = 2r_b b - b^2$$

$$b^2 - c^2 = 2r_b b - 2r_a c$$

$$(b - c)(b + c) = 2r_b b - 2r_a c$$

Furthermore, since $b + c = a$, we can express b as $a - c$ and substitute $a - c$ for b.

$$(a - c - c)(a - c + c) = 2r_b(a - c) - 2r_a c$$

$$(a - 2c)a = 2r_b a - 2r_b c - 2r_a c$$

$$a^2 - 2ca = 2r_b a - 2r_b c - 2r_a c$$

$$a^2 - 2r_b a = 2ca - 2r_b c - 2r_a c$$

$$a^2 - 2r_b a = c(2a - 2r_b - 2r_a)$$

$$c = \frac{a^2 - 2r_b a}{2a - 2r_b - 2r_a} = \frac{a(a - 2r_b)}{2a - 2(r_b + r_a)}$$

The length c is calculated in relation to the radius of the circles and the length |EF|. We can also find the height h using the length c, and thus calculate the height h using the radius and the length |EF|. In this case;

When the relationship between the radii of the circles is accepted as $r_a \geq r_b$.

$$h^2 = r_a^2 - (r_a - c)^2$$

$$= r_a^2 - \left(r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)} \right)^2$$

$$h = \sqrt{r_a^2 - \left(r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)} \right)^2}$$

When we substitute the value of h, which is related to the radius of the circles and the length |EF|, into the expression $\frac{a \cdot h}{2}$ that we use to find the area of the triangle;

The area of triangle CEF is expressed as:

$$= \frac{a}{2} \cdot \sqrt{r_a^2 - \left(r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)} \right)^2}$$

Therefore, the area of the CEDF quadrilateral is also $\frac{a \cdot h}{2}$, which is a.h. Hence, the area of the CEDF quadrilateral

$$= a \cdot \sqrt{r_a^2 - \left(r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)} \right)^2}$$

The formula for the area of a quadrilateral formed within the intersection region created by moving any two circles with given radii towards each other along a line passing through their centres, which varies according to the length of the diagonal on the line passing through the centres of the circles;

$$\text{The area of the quadrilateral Q.A.} = a \cdot \sqrt{r_a^2 - \left(r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)} \right)^2}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, the intersection region formed by moving two circles with given radius lengths towards each other along a line passing through their centres was examined. A quadrilateral structure was defined by connecting the intersection points obtained by joining the line segment formed by connecting the intersection points with the intersection points on the line passing through the centres. Area calculations were performed using the diagonals of this quadrilateral.

In this study, the intersection region was formed by moving any two circles with given radius lengths towards each other on a straight line passing through their centres. A quadrilateral was drawn in this intersection region, considering the line segment formed by joining the points where the circles intersect as the diagonal. The area was calculated using this diagonal of the quadrilateral and the diagonal on the line passing through the centres of the circles.

The relationship between the radius lengths of the circles and the diagonal length of the quadrilateral was examined. As a result of the analyses, an area formula was developed based on the relationship between the radius lengths of the circles (r_a ve r_b) and the diagonal length (a) on the line passing through the centres. The obtained formula was found to be valid for the intersection regions of both circles with equal radii and circles with different radii. Furthermore, it was determined that the area of the quadrilateral formed in the intersection region first increases, reaches a maximum value, and then decreases, depending on the relative position of the circles. This situation reveals the intersection points of geometric symmetry and algebraic relationships.

Figure 15. Area of the quadrilateral formed in the intersection region

The area of the quadrilateral formed in the region where the circles intersect was found by bringing any two circles closer to each other on the line passing through their centres, as shown in Figure 15, using the formula $(Q.A. = a \cdot \sqrt{r_a^2 - (r_a - \frac{a(a-2r_b)}{2a-2(r_b+r_a)})^2})$. The areas of the desired quadrilaterals can be calculated by specifying the radius lengths ($|AC| = r_a$ and $|CF| = r_b$) and the length of the line segment ($|EF| = a$) where the intersection region and the line d passing through the centres of the circles intersect.

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